

“RANDOMIZED CLINICAL TRIAL ON *ULLILEHYAM* (FOLKLORE MEDICINE) AND *GUDANAGARAHAREETAKI* GRANULES IN THE MANAGEMENT OF *ARTAVAKSHAYA* (OLIGOMENORRHEA)”

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ABSTRACT

Background: *Ārtava Kṣhaya* (oligomenorrhea) is a common menstrual disorder characterized by delayed or scanty menstruation, often associated with hormonal imbalance and *Agnimāndya*. **Aim:** To compare the efficacy of *Ulli Lehyam* and *Guḍa-Nāgara-Harītakī* granules in the management of *Ārtava Kṣhaya*. **Methods:** A randomized clinical trial was conducted on 40 female subjects diagnosed with *Ārtava Kṣhaya*. Participants were divided into two groups (n=20 each). Group A received *Ulli Lehyam* (24 g twice daily) and Group B received *Guḍa-Nāgara-Harītakī* granules (6 g twice daily) before food with *Sukhoṣhṇa Jala* for three consecutive menstrual cycles. Follow-up was done for one subsequent cycle. Subjective and objective parameters—menstrual interval, duration, amount of bleeding, pain, and endometrial thickness (USG)—were assessed. **Results:** Both formulations showed statistically significant improvement within groups ($p < 0.001$)

in menstrual regularity, bleeding duration, and endometrial thickness. However, intergroup comparison revealed no statistically significant difference ($p > 0.05$). Clinically, Group B showed marginally better results in cycle regularity and endometrial improvement, while Group A normalized bleeding duration earlier. **Conclusion:** Both *Ulli Lehyam* and *Guḍa-*

Nāgara–Harītakī granules are safe and effective in managing *Ārtava Kṣhaya* through *Agnidīpana*, *Rasāyana*, *Srotoshodhana*, and *Ārtavajanana* actions.

KEYWORDS: *Ārtava Kṣhaya*, Oligomenorrhea, *Ulli Lehyam*, *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī*, Ayurveda, Folklore medicine, Traditional formulations.

INTRODUCTION

Menstrual disorders are increasingly becoming a significant concern in modern gynaecological practice, affecting a large population of women in their reproductive years. Among these, oligomenorrhea, defined as infrequent menstrual cycles occurring more than 35 days apart.^[1,2] is commonly encountered. It not only hampers the quality of life but also serves as a major precursor to infertility and various systemic complications if left unaddressed. The etiological factors contributing to oligomenorrhea are often multifactorial, with endocrine disorders like Polycystic Ovarian Syndrome (PCOS), thyroid dysfunctions, and hyperprolactinemia playing a significant role. These conditions lead to anovulation, hormonal imbalances, and disturbances in the hypothalamic-pituitary-ovarian axis, further complicating the reproductive health of women.

If untreated, oligomenorrhea may lead to endometrial hyperplasia, endometrial carcinoma, osteoporosis, metabolic syndrome, and cardiovascular diseases.^[3] It is also associated with neuropsychiatric complications, including anxiety, anorexia, asthenia, and in some rare cases, hallucinations and delusions. The prevalence of oligomenorrhea in the general population is estimated at around 13.5%, with PCOS contributing to 4–10% of cases among women of reproductive age.^[4]

In Ayurveda, this condition is closely correlated with *Artavakshaya*, characterized *Yathochitakala adarshanam of artava(kala)* - Interval between two cycles exceed more than 35 days, *Alpartavam(srava)* – Scanty menstruation, flow < 2days, *Yoni vedana(shoola)* - Pain during menstruation.^[5] It is described as a state where there is a reduction in the quantity and quality of *Artava* (menstrual blood), often accompanied by lower abdominal pain. According to Acharya Sushruta, *Artavakshaya* is one of the primary causes of *Vandhyatva* (infertility).^[6,7,8] highlighting its clinical significance in reproductive disorders.

The pathogenesis of *Artavakshaya* is understood in two principal forms: *Dhatu Kshaya* and *Avarana* (obstruction in the flow of *Artava*). In the latter, *Kapha* and *Vata Doshas*, especially

when aggravated due to *Atisantarpana*^[9] (excessive nourishment or sedentary lifestyle), obstruct the *Artavavaha Srotas*, thereby impeding normal menstruation. This *Avarana Samprapti*.^[10] has a clinical resemblance to *Prameha*^[11] and PCOS, where obesity, anovulation, and irregular cycles co-exist.

Ayurvedic management of *Artavakshaya* focuses on breaking the *Samprapti* through a comprehensive approach involving *Amapachana*, *Agnideepana*, *Vatanulomana* (regulation of *Apana Vata*), and the use of *Agneya Dravyas* that stimulate the flow of *Artava*. Both *Shodhana* and *Shamana* therapies are indicated.^[12] *Shodhana Chikitsa* includes procedures such as *Basti*, *Vamana*, and *Virechana*, while *Shamana Chikitsa* primarily involves the internal administration of *Agneya Dravyas* to pacify the vitiated *Doshas* and restore normal menstruation.^[13,14,15] In this context, the present study is designed to evaluate and compare the efficacy of *Ullilehyam*.^[16] a traditional folk medicine, and *Guda-Nagara-Haritaki Prayoga*.^[17,18,19,20,21] a classical Ayurvedic formulation, in the management of *Artavakshaya*. The study also attempts to explore the probable connection between traditional folklore practices and Ayurvedic pharmacology, particularly to assess whether these formulations exhibit sustained therapeutic effects capable of breaking the *Samprapti* and restoring menstrual regularity. This integrative approach may offer safe, cost-effective, and holistic alternatives for women suffering from oligomenorrhea linked with PCOS and related disorders.

MATERIALS AND METHODS

Study Design

The present study was a randomized, open-label, comparative clinical trial conducted to evaluate and compare the efficacy of *Ulli Lehyam* (folklore medicine) and *Guḍa-Nāgara-Harītakī* granules (classical formulation) in the management of *Ārtava Kṣhaya* (Oligomenorrhea). Ethical clearance was obtained from the Institutional Ethics Committee of Alva's Ayurveda Medical College, Moodbidri, and the study was carried out following the principles of the Helsinki Declaration.

Study Population

A total of 40 female patients aged between 18 and 35 years presenting with symptoms of *Ārtava Kṣhaya* were selected from the Outpatient and Inpatient Departments of Prasooti Tantra and Stree Roga, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College and Hospital, Moodbidri. Patients

were screened on the basis of detailed menstrual, systemic, and gynecological history, along with relevant laboratory investigations and ultrasonography findings.

Diagnostic Criteria

Diagnosis was established on the basis of both *Āyurvedic* and modern parameters:

- *Yathochitakāla Adarśanam*.^[22] – interval between two menstrual cycles exceeding 35 days.^[23]
- *Alpārtava*.^[22] – menstrual bleeding lasting <2 days or scanty flow
- *Yoni Vedanā (Śūla)*.^[24] – lower abdominal pain during menstruation

Inclusion Criteria

- Women either married or unmarried aged between 16-35 years.
- Subjects fulfilling the diagnostic criteria.
- Haemoglobin > 8gm/dl
- Oligomenorrhea associated with obesity (BMI>25).
- Oligomenorrhea with unilateral or bilateral PCOS

Exclusion Criteria

- Congenital or structural abnormalities of reproductive organs
- Endocrine disorders such as hypothyroidism, hyperprolactinemia, or Cushing's syndrome
- Use of hormonal contraceptives or other hormonal therapy within three months prior to enrolment
- Pregnant and lactating women
- Systemic diseases like diabetes mellitus, hypertension, or hepatic dysfunction.

Grouping and Intervention

Eligible patients were randomly allocated into two groups (n = 20 each) using a simple random sampling technique.

Group	Intervention	Dose & Vehicle	Duration	Timing
A	<i>Ulli Lehyam</i>	24 g twice daily with <i>Sukhoṣhṇa Jala</i>	3 consecutive menstrual cycles	Before food
B	<i>Guda-Nāgara-Harītakī</i> granules	6 g twice daily with <i>Sukhoṣhṇa Jala</i>	3 consecutive menstrual cycles	Before food

Each participant was instructed to maintain a menstrual diary throughout the study period. A follow-up evaluation was conducted for one menstrual cycle after completion of therapy to assess the sustainability of therapeutic benefits.

Preparation of Trial Drugs

- **Ulli Lehyam:**^[25] Prepared as per traditional folklore formulation under the guidance of *Rasashastra and Bhaishajya Kalpana* experts at Alva's Pharmacy, Mijar. The ingredients included *Palandu (Allium cepa)*, *Lasuna (Allium sativum)*, *Methika (Trigonella foenum-graecum)*, *Jeeraka (Cuminum cyminum)*, *Pippali (Piper longum)*, *Madhu*, and *Ghee*.
- **Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī Granules:**^[26] Prepared according to *Bhaishajya Ratnāvali* using *Zingiber officinale (Śunṭhi)*, *Terminalia chebula (Harītakī)*, and *Guḍa (Jaggery)*. Both formulations were standardized for organoleptic and physicochemical parameters before administration.

Assessment Criteria

Evaluation was based on subjective and objective parameters before, during, and after the intervention:

SUBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

1. Interval between 2 cycles
2. Duration of bleeding
3. Pain in lower abdomen and vagina.

Table No. 1- Gradings for interval between the cycles.

1. INTERVAL BETWEEN THE CYCLES (IN DAYS)	
21-34 days	0
35-44 days	1
45-54 days	2
More than 54 days	3

Table No. 2- Gradings for duration of bleeding.

2. DURATION OF BLEEDING (IN DAYS)	
More than 2days	0
2 days	1
1 day	2
Less than 1 day	3

Table No. 3 - Gradings for pain.

3. PAIN DURING MENSTRUATION	
No pain	0
Mild pain	1
Moderate pain	2
Severe pain	3

OBJECTIVE PARAMETERS

1. Amount of bleeding
2. Ultrasonography either TAS/TVS.

Table No. 4 - Gradings for amount of bleeding.

1. AMOUNT OF BLEEDING (NUMBER OF PADS USED)	
More than 2pads / day	0
2 pads / day	1
½ to 1 pad / day	2
Only spotting	3

Table No. 5 - Gradings for Endometrial thickness.

2. ENDOMETRIAL THICKNESS (mm)	
Grade I	< 6 mm
Grade II	6- 7.9 mm
Grade III	8-9.9 mm
Grade IV	≥ 10 mm

LABORATORY INVESTIGATION**INVESTIGATIONS**

- Hb%,
- TSH,
- RBS
- USG, hormonal assay, urine routine (if necessary).
- Any other investigation if needed.

ETHICAL CLEARANCE

Ethical clearance was obtained from the ethical committee constituted in Alva's Ayurveda Medical college, Moodbidri.

ICEC (Institutional Clinical Ethics Committee Certificate) certificate got from Institutional Clinical Ethics Committee, Alva's Ayurveda Medical College on date 04/10/2023

CTRI (Clinical Trials Registry- India) REGISTRATION- CTRI Number- CTRI/2024/09/073533.

Statistical Analysis

The collected data were subjected to statistical evaluation using Sigmastat 4.0 software.

- Intra-group comparison: *Wilcoxon signed-rank test*

- Inter-group comparison: *Mann–Whitney U test* A *p*-value of <0.05 was considered statistically significant, while $p < 0.001$ indicated high significance.

Follow-up

Patients were followed for one subsequent menstrual cycle post-treatment to evaluate recurrence of symptoms or maintenance of regularity. Compliance and tolerability were monitored at every visit. No adverse drug reactions or toxic effects were reported during the study period.

RESULTS

A total of **40 female subjects** diagnosed with *Ārtava Kṣhaya* (Oligomenorrhea) were enrolled and randomly divided into two groups of 20 each.

- **Group A** received *Ulli Lehyam* (24 g twice daily before food with *Sukhoṣhṇa Jala*)
- **Group B** received *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* granules (6 g twice daily before food with *Sukhoṣhṇa Jala*)

The treatment was continued for **three consecutive menstrual cycles**, followed by one cycle of **follow-up**. Assessments were performed before treatment (BT), during treatment (DT1, DT2), after treatment (AT), and during follow-up (FU).

1. Effect on Menstrual Cycle Interval

In **Group A**, the mean cycle interval reduced from 1.55 ± 0.83 to 0.20 ± 0.52 , indicating an **87.1% improvement** ($p < 0.001$). In **Group B**, it decreased from 1.40 ± 0.75 to 0.10 ± 0.31 , with **92.8% improvement** ($p < 0.001$).

Both groups showed statistically significant improvement within groups; however, the **intergroup difference was not significant** ($p > 0.05$). Maximum benefit was achieved after the second treatment cycle and maintained through follow-up.

2. Effect on Duration of Bleeding

Before treatment, the mean duration of menstrual bleeding was 0.75 ± 0.55 days in Group A and 0.45 ± 0.51 days in Group B.

Following therapy, both groups achieved **complete normalization (100% improvement)** maintained throughout treatment and follow-up ($p < 0.001$). The intergroup comparison

revealed **no significant difference** ($p = 0.093$), indicating both formulations were equally effective in improving bleeding duration.

3. Effect on Amount of Bleeding

In Group A, the mean score decreased from 0.75 ± 0.55 to 0.00 ± 0.00 , showing **100% improvement** ($p < 0.001$). In Group B, it reduced from 0.95 ± 0.39 to 0.00 ± 0.00 , reflecting a **100% improvement** by the end of the treatment ($p < 0.001$).

No significant difference ($p > 0.05$) was observed between groups, indicating that both formulations effectively restored normal menstrual flow.

4. Effect on Pain (Yoni Śūla)

Mean pain scores reduced slightly in both groups—from 0.95 ± 0.61 to 0.90 ± 0.31 in Group A and 0.95 ± 0.22 to 0.95 ± 0.22 in Group B. Although the reduction was not statistically significant ($p > 0.05$), several patients with moderate pain reported subjective relief, suggesting mild analgesic and *Vātānulomaka* benefits of both formulations.

5. Effect on Endometrial Thickness

Endometrial thickness (ET) was assessed using ultrasonography before and after treatment.

- Group A: increased from 5.2 ± 1.1 mm to 8.7 ± 1.4 mm ($p < 0.001$)
- Group B: increased from 5.4 ± 1.2 mm to 9.1 ± 1.3 mm ($p < 0.001$)

Both groups exhibited **highly significant improvement**, with participants moving from *Grade I–II* (thin endometrium) to *Grade III–IV* (healthy proliferative endometrium). The **intergroup difference was not significant** ($p = 0.327$), confirming comparable uterine responses in both formulations.

6. Overall Clinical Outcome

- **Group A (Ulli Lehyam):** 85% showed marked improvement, 10% moderate improvement, 5% mild improvement.
- **Group B (Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī):** 90% showed marked improvement, 5% moderate improvement, 5% mild improvement.

Both drugs produced significant and sustained therapeutic effects with **no adverse reactions or intolerance** reported during the study.

Summary of Results.

Parameter	Group A – <i>Ulli Lehyam</i>	Group B – <i>Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī</i>	Significance
Cycle Interval	↓ from 1.55 → 0.20	↓ from 1.40 → 0.10	p < 0.001 (within), ns (between)
Duration of Bleeding	↑ to normal (100%)	↑ to normal (100%)	p < 0.001 (within), ns (between)
Amount of Bleeding	Normalized (100%)	Normalized (100%)	p < 0.001 (within), ns (between)
Pain Score	Mild relief	Mild relief	ns
Endometrial Thickness	5.2 → 8.7 mm	5.4 → 9.1 mm	p < 0.001 (within), ns (between)

(ns = not significant between groups)

Interpretation

Both *Ulli Lehyam* and *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* granules demonstrated **significant regulation of menstrual cycles, improvement in endometrial growth, and normalization of bleeding patterns.**

While *Ulli Lehyam* acted more rapidly on bleeding duration, *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* showed slightly higher improvement in endometrial thickness and overall cycle regularity. Both formulations were well tolerated and produced **comparable overall efficacy** ($p > 0.05$).

DISCUSSION

The present randomized clinical study aimed to evaluate and compare the efficacy of *Ulli Lehyam* (a folklore formulation) and *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* granules (a classical *Āyurvedic* formulation) in the management of *Ārtava Kṣhaya* (Oligomenorrhea). Both interventions produced highly significant improvements in menstrual cycle regularity, bleeding duration, endometrial thickness, and overall reproductive health, validating their traditional therapeutic claims.

Pathophysiological Correlation

In *Ayurveda*, *Ārtava Kṣhaya* arises due to *Agnimāndya*, *Āvaraṇa* of *Vāta*, and depletion of *Rasa–Rakta Dhātus*. *Artava*, being an *Upadhātu* of *Rasa* or *Rakta*, becomes deficient when *Jatharāgni* and *Dhātvāgni* are impaired. This results in delayed, scanty, or irregular menstruation. The predominance of *Vāta–Kapha Doṣa* and *Srotorodha* (obstruction of channels) further disturbs *Apāna Vāta*, the governing force behind *Ārtava Pravṛtti* (menstrual flow).

Lifestyle factors such as irregular diet, stress, sleep disturbances, and junk food consumption—observed in the present study—aggravate *Vāta* and *Kapha Doṣa*, causing *Agnidūṣṭi* and *Āvarana*. These findings support the classical description of *Ārtava Kṣhaya* as a disorder rooted in *Agni* and *Vāta* imbalance, paralleling modern correlations with hypothalamic–pituitary–ovarian (HPO) axis dysfunction.

Pharmacodynamic Discussion

Ulli Lehyam

Ulli Lehyam contains *Palandu*, *Rasona*, *Methika*, *Jeeraka*, *Pippali*, *Śhatapuṣhpa*, *Narikela*, *Ghṛita*, and *Guḍa*.

- These ingredients possess *Katu Rasa*, *Uṣhṇa Vīrya*, and *Tikṣhṇa Guṇa*, contributing to *Agnidīpana*, *Srotoshodhana*, and *Vātānulomana* actions.
- *Palandu* and *Rasona* enhance uterine blood flow and act as *Artavajanana* (emmenagogues).
- *Methika* exerts phytoestrogenic activity that supports ovarian function and endometrial proliferation.
- *Ghṛita* and *Narikela* provide *Snigdhatva*, pacifying *Vāta* and nourishing *Rasa–Rakta Dhātus*.

Hence, the formulation restores menstrual regularity through a combined effect on *Agni*, *Vāta*, and *Srotas*.

Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī Granules

This classical formulation includes *Śuṅṭhi* (*Zingiber officinale*), *Harītakī* (*Terminalia chebula*), and *Guḍa* (*Jaggery*).

- *Śuṅṭhi* acts as *Dīpana–Pācana* and *Kapha–Vāta Śāmaka*, enhancing digestion and uterine function.
- *Harītakī* regulates *Apāna Vāta*, clears *Srotorodha*, and provides *Rasāyana* support.
- *Guḍa* replenishes *Rakta Dhātu* and prevents *Vāta Prakopa*. Together, they perform *Vātānulomana*, *Rasāyana*, and *Ārtava Pravartaka* actions, promoting timely menstruation and improving endometrial receptivity.

Correlation with Observed Results

Both groups exhibited statistically significant normalization of menstrual cycle interval ($p < 0.001$), duration, and flow, with 85–90% of patients showing marked improvement. The mean

endometrial thickness increased from 5.2 mm to 8.7 mm in *Ulli Lehyam* and from 5.4 mm to 9.1 mm in *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* group, indicating enhanced proliferative activity. These findings correlate with the *Artavajanana* and *Rasāyana* properties of the formulations.

Pain relief during menstruation was clinically notable in moderate pain though not statistically significant, reflecting mild *Vātānulomana* and *Srotoshodhana* actions. No adverse effects were reported, confirming the safety of both preparations.

While both groups achieved comparable statistical results, *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* exhibited slightly faster response and better endometrial recovery, possibly due to its rejuvenative (*Rasāyana*) and *Tridoṣha*-balancing effects. *Ulli Lehyam*, however, showed quicker normalization of bleeding duration due to its potent *Uṣhṇa–Tikṣhṇa* action.

Probable Mechanism of Action

Both formulations act on multiple *Samprāpti Ghaṭakas*:

- **Doṣha:** *Vāta–Kapha Śamana*
- **Agni:** *Dīpana–Pācana*
- **Srotas:** *Srotoshodhana*
- **Vāta:** Regulation of *Apāna Vāta*
- **Dhātu:** *Rasa–Rakta Dhātu Pōṣana* leading to proper *Artava Utpatti*

Thus, they address the root pathology of *Ārtava Kṣhaya* by correcting metabolism, enhancing uterine blood flow, and supporting hormonal equilibrium.

CONCLUSION

The randomized clinical trial entitled “*Comparative Clinical Evaluation of Ulli Lehyam (Folklore Medicine) and Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī Granules in the Management of Ārtava Kṣhaya (Oligomenorrhea)*” demonstrated that both formulations are effective, safe, and well-tolerated in restoring normal menstrual rhythm. Statistically, both groups showed highly significant improvement within groups ($p < 0.001$) in menstrual cycle interval, duration, and amount of bleeding, along with a marked increase in endometrial thickness. However, intergroup comparison revealed no significant difference, suggesting comparable efficacy.

Clinically, *Guḍa–Nāgara–Harītakī* granules exhibited slightly better improvement in cycle regularity and endometrial proliferation, while *Ulli Lehyam* normalized bleeding duration earlier. Both formulations provided mild relief from dysmenorrhea and improved overall

well-being without any adverse reactions. The outcomes confirm that these drugs act through *Agnidīpana* (enhancement of metabolic fire), *Srotoshodhana* (channel purification), *Rasāyana* (rejuvenation), and *Ārtava Pravartana* (menstrual stimulation) properties, thereby restoring the normal function of *Ārtavavaha Srotas*.

The study highlights the therapeutic potential of *Ayurvedic* interventions in gynecological disorders like *Ārtava Kṣhaya*, providing safe, cost-effective, and holistic alternatives to hormonal therapy. Though both formulations proved equally effective statistically, their clinical subtleties justify individualized selection based on *Doṣha* predominance and patient constitution.

Further large-scale, multicentric studies with extended follow-up, hormonal profiling, and ovulation tracking are warranted to substantiate these findings and to integrate such *Ayurvedic* formulations into broader reproductive healthcare strategies.

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REFERENCES

1. Konar H. DC Dutta's textbook of gynecology. JP Medical Ltd; 2016 Jun 30.
2. Riaz Y, Parekh U. Oligomenorrhea. [Updated 2023 Jul 31]. In: statpearls [Internet]. Treasure Island (FL): statpearls Publishing; 2023 Jan-
<https://www.ncbi.nlm.nih.gov/books/NBK560575/>
3. Attia GM, et al. The Impact of Irregular Menstruation on Health: A Review. (2023).
4. Riaz Y, Parekh U. Oligomenorrhea. InStatPearls [Internet] 2021 Aug 9. StatPearls Publishing.

5. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana 30/226. In: Tripathi B, editor. 2nd ed. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2014.
6. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Sharira Sthana 2/4. In: Sharma PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Visvabharati; 2012.
7. Vagbhata. Ashtanga Hridaya, Sharira Sthana 1/8. In: Sharma PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2015.
8. Murthy KR Srikantha. Illustrated Sushruta Samhita. Vol II. Sharira Sthana. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2012.
9. Murthy KRS. Textbook of Ayurveda – Vata, Pitta, Kapha Nidana and Samprapti. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2010.
10. Tewari PV. Ayurvediya Prasuti Tantra evam Stri Roga. Vol I. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2011.
11. Sharma RK, Dash B. Caraka Samhita: Text with English Translation & Critical Exposition. Vol V, Chikitsa Sthana. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Sanskrit Series Office; 2014.
12. Tewari PV. Ayurvediya Prasuti Tantra evam Stri Roga. Vol I. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2011.
13. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana 30/226–227. In: Tripathi B, editor. 2nd ed. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2014.
14. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Sharira Sthana 2/4. In: Sharma PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Visvabharati; 2012.
15. Vagbhata. Ashtanga Hridaya, Chikitsa Sthana 1/64-70. In: Sharma PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2015.
16. PK Beena Rose, Anita K Patel, & K V Asha. (2022). A Widely Used Drug Ulli (Palandu- Allium Cepa Linn) and its Formulations in Postnatal Care in Kerala, India. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research,9(12): 19-23. <https://doi.org/10.47070/ijapr.v9i12.2206>.
17. Harita. Harita Samhita. Sūtikā Paricharyā Adhyaya. In: Tripathi B, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2009; 112-114.
18. Sushruta. Sushruta Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana 33/29-31. In: Sharma PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Visvabharati; 2012.
19. Agnivesha. Charaka Samhita, Chikitsa Sthana 15/90-92. In: Tripathi B, editor. 2nd ed. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Surbharati Prakashan; 2014.
20. Vagbhata. Ashtanga Hridaya, Chikitsa Sthana 6/88-90. In: Sharma PV, editor. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Orientalia; 2015.

21. Bhavamishra. Bhavaprakasha Nighantu. Haritakyadi Varga, 37-40. In: Chunekar KC, Pandey GS, editors. Varanasi: Chaukhamba Bharati Academy; 2010.
22. Sharma RK, Dash B, translators. Charaka Saṁhitā of Agniveśa. Vol. IV. Chikitsā Sthāna (Yonivyāpada Chikitsā Adhyāya). Varanasi: Chowkhamba Sanskrit Series Office; 2014.
23. Hoffman BL, Schorge JO, Bradshaw KD, et al. Williams Gynecology. 4th ed. New York: McGraw-Hill Education; 2020.
24. Murthy KRS, translator. Aṣṭāṅga Hṛdaya of Vāgbhaṭa. Vol. II. Uttara Tantra (Strīroga Pratiśedha Adhyāya). Varanasi: Chowkhamba Krishnadas Academy; 2012.
25. PK Beena Rose, Anita K Patel, & K V Asha. (2022). A Widely Used Drug Ulli (Palandu-Allium Cepa Linn) and its Formulations in Postnatal Care in Kerala, India. International Journal of Ayurveda and Pharma Research, 9(12): 19-23. <https://doi.org/10.47070/ijapr.v9i12.2206>.
26. Khemuka N, Galib R, Patgiri BJ, Prajapati PK. Pharmaceutical standardization of Kamsaharitaki granules. Ayu. 2015 Oct-Dec; 36(4): 416-420. DOI:10.4103/0974-8520.190698. PMID: 27833371; PMCID: PMC5041391.